

Perspectives in Labor Economics Journal : Technical Note and Journal Presentation

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Published: Dec 28, 2025

Journal url: <https://alfarabipublishing.com/index.php/PLE>

Abstract

This technical note describes the editorial scope, publishing policies, and technical infrastructure of the Journal Perspectives in Labor Economics.

It is published for documentation and transparency purposes only and does not constitute a peer-reviewed research article.

Introduction

Perspectives in Labor Economics Journal, addressing transformations in employment and labor markets.

This document presents the website, scope, and editorial orientation of the Perspectives in Labor Economics Journal, published by Al-Farabi Publishing and Research.

It is intended for technical, descriptive, and archiving purposes only.

This document is not a peer-reviewed research article and does not constitute an official journal issue.

Aims and Scope

The mission of *Perspectives in Labor Economics Journal* is to foster research and reflection on the role of labor dynamics in economic development, social regulation, and public policy. The journal welcomes a wide range of topics, structured around the following themes:

- **Labor market functioning:** analysis of labor supply and demand, wage formation, unemployment, underemployment, informality, and occupational mobility.
- **Labor institutions and regulation:** the role of trade unions, collective bargaining, wage policies, and labor legislation in regulating the labor market.

- **Education, skills, and human capital:** the effects of education, vocational training, reskilling, and skill development on employability and productivity.
- **Inequalities and labor market segmentation:** gender, age, status, and origin-based inequalities; segmentation between stable and precarious jobs; discrimination and unequal access to opportunities.
- **Employment policies and social protection:** evaluation of public policies designed to stimulate employment, reduce unemployment, protect vulnerable workers, and support professional transitions.
- **Labor and globalization:** the impact of international trade, foreign investment, and global value chains on employment, wages, and working conditions.
- **Technology, digitalization, and the future of work:** the effects of automation, artificial intelligence, and platform economies on jobs and forms of work.
- **Industrial relations and social dialogue:** dynamics between employers and employees, transformations in trade unionism, collective bargaining, and social mediation.
- **Labor and well-being:** analysis of job quality, stress, occupational health, work-life balance, and determinants of worker well-being.
- **International and interdisciplinary comparisons:** cross-country studies on labor dynamics in developed, emerging, and developing economies; contributions from related disciplines such as sociology, law, management, and political science.

Open Access Statement

The journal follows a **full open access policy**. All published articles are immediately available to the scientific community and the general public without subscription or access restrictions. This policy serves three main objectives:

1. **Promote knowledge dissemination** by removing financial barriers for readers.
2. **Enhance author visibility** by offering them a global audience including researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.
3. **Contribute to open science** by enabling the reuse and dissemination of published works in academic, educational, and societal contexts.

Published articles are archived in digital libraries and open databases, ensuring their long-term preservation, traceability, and accessibility.

Publication Ethics

Any misconduct—including plagiarism, data manipulation or falsification, self-plagiarism, or redundant publication—results in sanctions ranging from manuscript rejection to future submission bans, or even retraction of already published articles.

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